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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF
GENERAL PUBLIC TOWARDS THE USE OF PAINKILLERS IN
BAHAWALPUR**¹Dr. Muhammad Arif, ²Dr Muhammad Saad Afzal, ³Dr Muhammad Ahmed²Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Teaching Hospital Gujrat³Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Abstract:**

One of the most widely used and abused drugs all over the world are painkillers, pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage. Pain can occur as an acute, chronic, or intermittent sensation, or as a combination of the three, and is reported to be the common reason for medical visit. Specific objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge and attitude of people regarding the use of painkillers and highlight the reason for improper use of painkillers in people of Bahawalpur. This was a cross-sectional questionnaire based survey. The study was conducted between Januarys to March 2018 in Bahawalpur Pakistan using a structured questionnaire. Data was taken from 412 residents of Bahawalpur those who were taking painkillers. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied by using SPSS version 20. 255 (61.9%) respondents were male and 157 (38.1%) respondents were female. 223 (54.1%) respondents were in 18-30 years of age group that is of maximum strength and 19 (4.6%) respondents were between 61-80 years that is minimum strength. 91 (22.1%) were maximum number of respondents those had above 35000 monthly income and 89 (21.6%) had income below 14000. Majority had knowledge about the use and side effect of painkillers they had positive attitude towards painkiller use. 80% of total respondents answered "yes" for the question if painkillers can relieve the fatigue and pain or not. (65.7%) of total said painkillers can relieve fever. (26.5%) responded with yes that it is appropriate to use painkillers in children less than 12 year. (57.5%) said painkillers can cause sleep disturbance, (47.5%) said shortness of breath, (74.6%) knew that painkillers can cause stomach ulcer. The frequency of pain experienced by most of the respondents 178 (44%) was once a month. (50.3%) used Panadol, respondents those who felt headache were 175 (43.2%). Most of the people used specific painkillers by the prescription of doctor. (74.1%) preferred to take painkillers in tablet/capsule form, (80.7%) took their medicine with water, (64.1%) bought painkiller from medical store. Result of study demonstrates that people of Bahawalpur had satisfactory knowledge about painkillers and had positive attitude towards painkillers majority knew the side effect of painkillers.

Key words: knowledge, attitude, side effect.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Muhammad Arif,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain is defined as the "unpleasant sensory and emotional experience with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage. Pain is the most prominent member of a class of sensations known as bodily sensations which includes itches, tickles, tingles, orgasms and so on. Pain is defined as a sensory and affective experience that has a protective function. A difference exists between "primary" and "secondary" stage pain effect. The secondary stage effect encompasses negative emotions like sadness, gloominess and depression caused by cognitive processes underlying the elaboration of meanings and the evaluation of the significance and the future implications of pain. The perception of clinical pain depends on the activity of the brain though there is no compelling evidence that responses to experimental painful stimuli can predict the pattern of brain responses in chronic clinical pain states. Lack of attention towards the painful stimuli may also result in no sensation of pain [1].

One of the most widely used and abused drugs all over the world are pain-killers, pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage [2]. Pain can be accomplished as an acute, chronic, or intermittent sensation, or as a combination of the three, and is reported to be the common reason for medical visit [3]. Postoperative pain is linked with patient recovery, satisfaction, and readmission after surgery [4]. Postoperative pain is a physiological result of stimulation of both the somatic and visceral pain pathways. Specialized nociceptors are stimulated by noxious stimuli released after tissue damage such as inflammatory mediators including bradykinin, serotonin, prostaglandins, and cytokines [5].

1.1 CONDITIONS FOR PAIN MEDICATIONS USE

Headache is a most common neurological complaint with profound bearing on one's personal, working and social life [6]. The most commonly reported physical symptoms are back pain, headache and tiredness. It results in a great deal of disability and distress especially in industrialized countries [7]. NSAIDs are widely used for pain and inflammation i.e. osteoarthritis[8]. NSAIDs also have been shown to be effective in orthopedic surgery; they decrease pain and inflammation, therefore allowing patients to have an increased knee range of motion, leading to a shorter period of physical therapy [5].

1.2 MANAGEMENT OF PAIN

Painkillers are the mainstay of management of pain, they are the most used and abused set of drugs globally. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are one of the most frequently prescribed drugs for pain management worldwide [9]. Painkillers (Analgesics) currently represent the mainstay of pain management, with an array of drugs available, aspirin, acetaminophen, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), mixed agonist and antagonists and narcotic analgesics [10]. Analgesics are the corner stone of pain management and paracetamol is relatively safe when taken in therapeutic dose (≤ 4 g/day for adults) [9].

1.2.1 NSAIDS

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are used by millions of people worldwide to neutralize pain, fever and inflammation [11]. NSAIDs can maintain a constant level of prostaglandin inhibition over the course of a prolonged surgery and during the postoperative period. They have no risk of abuse; therefore, postoperative use of NSAIDs helps reduce growing concerns of opioid abuse and the potential over-prescription of opiate [5]. NSAIDs and paracetamol are most commonly the first line pharmacotherapy in combating different pain and inflammatory disorder and fever [12]. Paracetamol is used for mild pain and as an anti-pyretic drug. The mechanism of action of paracetamol is not clearly known, although one theory suggests that it acts as a selective inhibitor of the cyclooxygenase enzyme isoform, COX-3, found in the brain and spinal cord. Unlike NSAIDs, it has no anti-inflammatory action [13]. Aspirin is a commonly used NSAID, mainly used for dental pain. Ibuprofen's anti-inflammatory effect is slightly weaker than aspirin and it has fewer side effects. It is taken for mild-to-moderate pain such as headaches and muscular/joint pains [14].

1.2.2 OPIOIDS

Opioids are drugs that are widely used in pain treatment worldwide and that the World Health Organization (WHO) considers essential for the control of moderate and intense pain particularly of oncological origin[15]. Opioids are drugs that produce morphine-like effects to reduce moderate or severe pain [16].

1.3 ADVERSE EFFECTS OF PAIN MEDICATIONS

ADRs are considered as the 4th to 6th leading causes of death among hospitalized patients. These are associated with significant morbidity, mortality and permanent disability and are a huge economic

burden on the patients due to prolonged hospitalization. It has been estimated that the incidence of ADRs throughout the world is 5% and 56% of all the hospital admissions which are caused by drug-induced problems [17]. The use of opioids is associated with various ADRs ranging from nausea and vomiting to urinary retention and respiratory depression [9]. Persistent use of analgesics has substantial economic costs, both for the individual and the society e.g. through reimbursement or the management of adverse effects [18]. People believe there is a pill for every illness, at the onset of all kinds of minor disorders; they immediately take analgesics, heavy use of analgesics particularly over-the-counter (OTC) products has long been associated with chronic renal failure. Several studies have reported associations between chronic renal failure and use of other forms of analgesics, including acetaminophen, aspirin, and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [19]. Over dosage of paracetamol leads to hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity [20].

METHADODOLOGY: STUDY DESIGN

A descriptive cross-sectional study was performed among general population of Bahawalpur, Pakistan. The study was conducted in general population of Pakistan targeted in Bahawalpur.

The most important aspect in conducting a study is determination of sample size. It is practically impossible and unjustifiable to include the whole population in any study. So a set of participants is chosen from the whole population which is less in number but sufficiently represents the whole population from which it is taken so that results can be generalized for the whole population

Sample size was determined by Rao soft sample calculator. Bahawalpur city has approximately 20,00,000 population, level of confidence is taken 95% and marginal error is 5%. By these parameters the recommended sample size is 385. 10% additional sample size is included to compensate while excluding improperly and partially filled questionnaires during the data cleaning process.

$$n = N \times \frac{z^2 \times p \times q}{(N-1)E^2 + z^2} \quad [21]$$

Convenient sampling method was used to select the respondents for the study on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

DATA ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis was performed by using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics was used to

summarize the data. Mean and standard deviation was calculated for the numerical variables. Chi square test was used to calculate p-value. Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test were applied to find significant difference between various tools score and categorical variable of socio demographic section.

RESULTS:

A total of 412 participants were included in the study from Bahawalpur. All the questionnaires were filled and included in the final analysis. According to the need and objectives of the study appropriate descriptive and inferential statistics were applied by using SPSS (version 20.0). Descriptive statistics (Percentages, frequencies, mean SD) was applied in order to summarize the data. In differential statistics, chi-square test was applied in order to evaluate association between independent and dependent variables. Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test were applied to find significant difference between various tools score and categorical variable of socio demographic section. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered as statistical significant level for the entire test while difference in score of respondent's knowledge level.

All the study results were carefully tabulated and interpreted in the following manner.

1.4 DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Table 4.1 shows the demographic details of study population. Sample size was 412. About 255 (61.9%) respondents were male and 157 (38.1%) respondents were female. About 223 (54.1%) respondents were in 18-30 years of age group that is maximum strength, 92 (22.3%) respondents were in 31-42 years of age group while 77 (18.7%) were in 43-60 years of age group and 19 (4.6%) respondents were in 61-80 years that is minimum strength. Regarding education status 34 (8.3%) were illiterate, 54 (13.1%) were at primary education level, at secondary level were 92 (22.3%), 88 (21.4) were at higher secondary level while at higher education level were 144(35%). According to job description 244 (59.2%) of the respondents were employed and 168 (40.8%) respondents were unemployed. Maximum respondents were 91 (22.1%) that had above 35000 monthly income, 80(19.4%) respondents were belong to income range 14000-25000, 35 (8.5%) respondents were belongs to 26000-35000 income range and 89 (21.6%) had income below 14000.

Table 4.1 DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	255	61.9
	Female	157	38.1
Total		412	
Age	18-30	223	54.1
	31-42	92	22.3
	43-60	77	18.7
	61-80	19	4.6
Total		412	
Level of Education	Illiterate	34	8.3
	Primary	54	13.1
	Secondary	92	22.3
	Higher sec.	88	21.4
	Higher education	144	35
Total		412	
Job description	Employed or Businessman	244	59.2
	Unemployed	168	40.8
Total		412	
Monthly Income	Below 14000	89	21.6
	14000-25000	80	19.4
	25000-35000	35	8.5
	Above 35000	91	22.1
Total		412	

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded.

1.5 ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE REGARDING USE OF PAINKILLERS AMONG THE RESPONDENTS

Table 4.2 shows Knowledge of general public of Bahawalpur about painkillers was assessed by asking simple questions regarding general knowledge, attitude and effect of painkillers. Most of the questions were designed as close ended and response was recorded as “Yes” or “No”, but some had options to be opened ended.

Majority had knowledge about the use and side effect of painkillers and they had positive attitude towards painkiller but some people had no sufficient knowledge about painkillers. 322 respondents knew and 80 did not know that painkillers can relieve the fatigue. 270 knew and 141 did not know that painkillers can relieve fever. 178 respond yes and 231 respond no to this question Do painkillers have anti-inflammatory effect? Respond were 72 yes and 340 no of question Is it safe to take painkillers with empty stomach 90 respondents knew and 322 did not know that it is safe to take painkillers for long term. 310 knew and 101 did not know that the long term use of painkillers can cause liver damage. 273 people knew and 136 did not know that painkillers can cause allergies in certain patients. 77 people responded yes and 327 people responded no to question is it safe to

use painkillers in pregnancy? 108 responded yes and 300 responded no to question is it appropriate to use painkillers in children less than 12 year. 234 people responded yes and 173 responded no to question “Can painkiller cause sleep disturbances”. 194 people responded yes and 214 responded no to “Can painkillers cause the shortness of breath”. 311 people knew and 96 did not know that pain killers can cause stomach ulcer. 168 responded yes and 242 respond no to the question “Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms?” 178 answered yes and 231 answered no about the question “Do you know the correct dose of your painkillers?” 389 answered yes and 23 answered no about the question “Have you ever suffered from pain?” 309 answered yes and 81 answered no about the question “Does pain affect your working ability?” 49 replied with yes and 345 with no “Do you take two or more painkillers in combination?” 166 came up with the answer yes and 227 said no about the question “Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers?” 40 answered yes and 355 answered no about “Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers?” 79 answered yes and 314 answered no about the

question“Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers?”

Table 4.2 ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE

Statement	Yes (N%)	No(N%)	Total (%)
Can painkillers relieve the fatigue?	332(80.4)	80(19.6)	412
Can painkillers relieve fever?	270(65.7)	141(34.3)	411
Do painkillers have anti-inflammatory effect?	178(43.5)	231(56.5)	409
Is it safe to take painkillers with empty stomach?	72(17.5)	340(82.5)	412
Is it safe to take painkillers for long term?	90(21.8)	322(78.2)	412
Can long term use of painkillers cause liver damage?	310(75.4)	101(24.6)	411
Can painkillers cause allergies in certain patients?	273(66.7)	136(33.3)	409
Is it safe to use painkillers in pregnancy?	77(19.1)	327(80.9)	404
Is it appropriate to use painkillers in children less than 12 years?	108(26.5)	300(73.5)	408
Can painkiller cause sleep disturbances?	234(57.5)	173(42.5)	407
Can painkillers cause the shortness of breath?	194(47.5)	214(52.5)	408
Can pain killers cause stomach ulcer?	311(76.4)	96(23.6)	407
Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms?	168(41)	242(59)	410
Do you know the correct dose of your painkillers?	178(43.5)	231(56.5)	409
Have you ever suffered from pain?	389(94.4)	23(5.6)	412
Does pain affect your working ability?	309(78.6)	81(20.6)	393
Do you take two or more painkillers in combination?	49(12.4)	345(87.6)	394
Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers?	166(42.2)	227(57.8)	393
Do you use painkillers for causes other than pain relieve?	40(10.1)	355(89.9)	395
Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers?	79(20)	314(80)	397

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded

1.6 THE ATTITUDE OF GENERAL PUBLIC OF BAHAWALPUR REGARDING PAIN KILLER USE

Table 4.3 shows the attitude of general public of Bahawalpur regarding use of painkillers. According to the table first three questions have 405 respondents. The frequency of pain experienced by most of the respondents 178 (44%) was once a month while 142 (35.1%) experience pain once a week, 71 (17.5%) experience pain every day while 13 (3.2%) had never experienced pain. Most of the respondents felt headache 175 (43.2%), 94 (23.2%) had back pain, 78 (19.3%) suffered from leg pain while 58 (14.3) suffered from other kinds of pain. 237 (58.5%) of the respondents treated pain by taking medicines, 112 (27.7%) treated pain by taking rest, 27 (6.7%) treated pain by taking massage, 17 (4.2%) treated pain by warm stroking while 12 (3%) treated their pain by other ways. Out of 394 respondents, the mostly used pain killer was Panadol 198 (50.3%), 74 (18.8%) respondents use Ponstan, 36 (9.1%) used Dispirine, 31(7.9%) used Dicloran, 25 (6.3%) respondent used Brufen, while 12(3%), 8 (2%) used Tramadol and Voltral respectively and 10 (2.5%) used other pain killers. Of the 394 respondents, 248 (62.9%) respondents took painkillers due to severe pain, 121

(30.7%) took painkillers due to moderate pain while 24 (6.1%) took painkillers due to mild pain. Most of the respondents 152 (38.6%) used specific painkillers as prescribed by the doctor, 149 (37.8%) use specific pain killer due to previous positive experience while 83(21.1%) used specific pain killer due to availability, 9 (2.3%) included in others. Out of the 394 respondents, 200 (50.8%) of the respondents used painkillers on advice of doctors, 83 (21.1%) used pain killer by themselves, 79 (20.1%) used painkillers on advice of family/friend, 21 (5.3%) used painkillers on advice of pharmacist while 11 (2.8%) used pain killers due to media/ads. Out of 394 respondents 292 (74.1%) preferred to take painkillers in tablet/capsule form, 57(14.5%) preferred to take painkillers in syrup form, 32(8.1%) preferred the injection form while 11(2.8) included in others. Out of 395 respondents 317(80.7%) took medicine with water, 38 (9.7%) took painkillers with milk, 32 (8.1%) took painkillers with tea while 6 (0.5%) were included in others. Out of 395 respondents, 253(64.1%) took pain killer from medical store, 64(16.2%) took painkillers from pharmacy, 38(9.6%) took medicine from government hospitals, 31(7.8%) took medicine from general store while 9(2.3%) took their medicine from herbal store.

Table 4.3 ATTITUDE OF PEOPLE TOWARD THE USE OF PAINKILLER

Statement	Response Options	N	%age
What is the frequency of the pain?	Daily	13	3.2
	Once in a week	142	35.1
	Once in month	178	44
	Never	71	17.5
Total		405	100
Which pain you feel mostly?	Headache	175	43.2
	Back Pain	94	23.2
	Leg Pain	78	19.3
	Others	58	14.3
Total		405	100
How do you treat your pain?	Rest	112	27.7
	Massage	27	6.7
	Warm Stroking	17	4.2
	Medicines	237	58.5
	Others	12	3
Total		405	100
Which painkiller you use mostly?	Panadol	198	50.3
	Ponstan	74	18.8
	Dicloran	31	7.9
	Dispirine	36	9.1
	Brufen	25	6.3
	Tramal	12	3
	Voltral	8	2
	Others	10	2.5
Total		394	100
Severity of pain that forces you to take painkillers?	Mild	24	6.1
	Moderate	121	30.7
	Severe	248	62.9
Total		394	100
Reason for choosing that specific painkiller?	Prescribed by doctor	152	38.6
	Due to availability	83	21.1
	Positive previous experience	149	37.8
	Others	9	2.3
Total		394	100

Table 4.3 continued.....

Statement	Response Options	N	%age
You use painkiller on the advice of?	Doctor	200	50.8
	Pharmacist	21	5.3
	Friends/Family	79	20.1
	Ads/Media	11	2.8
	By yourself	83	21.1
Total		394	100
What is your preferable dosage form?	Tablet/Capsule	292	74.1
	Injection	32	8.1
	Syrup	57	14.5
	Others	11	2.8
Total		394	100
Mostly you used your painkillers with?	Water	317	80.7
	Tea	32	8.1
	Milk	38	9.7
	Others	6	.5
Total		394	100
From where you get your painkillers?	Pharmacy	64	16.2
	Medical Store	253	64.1
	Govt. Hospital	38	9.6
	General Store	31	7.8
	Herbal Store	9	2.3
Total		395	100

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded.

1.7 ASSOCIATION OF KNOWLEDGE WITH GENDER

Association of gender with knowledge shows insignificant difference. Most of respondents (80.6%) said painkillers can relieve fatigue. 65.7 of the total respondents said painkillers can relieve fever. 67.4% of the total respondents knew that painkillers can become a cause of stomach ulcers. 67.7% of the respondents said could cause allergies. There was no significant difference between the knowledge of males and females.

ASSOCIATION OF ATTITUDE WITH GENDER

Table 4.4 shows the association off attitude with gender. We analyzed the association of attitude with gender and there was great influence of gender on attitude about the use of painkillers. Male and female attitude was greatly different from each other. 38.9% Of the total male respondents knew the correct dose of painkillers while in case of female's percentage was 51%. Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers, Male; yes: 42.2% and Female; yes: 48.7%. 65.9% of the males treated their pain with medicines while in case of female this percentage was 46.8.

Table 4.4 ASSOCIATION OF ATTITUDE WITH GENDER

Statement		Male	Female	Total	P
Do you know the correct dose of painkiller	Yes	98(38.9)	80(51)	178(43.5)	.017
	No	154(61.1)	77(49)	231(56.5)	
Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms	Yes	106(41.9)	62(39.5)	168(41)	.630
	No	147(58.1)	95(60.5)	242(59)	
Have You ever suffered from pain	Yes	241(94.5)	148(94.3)	389(94.4)	.917
	No	14(5.5)	9(5.7)	23(5.6)	
Does pain affect your working ability	Yes	183(77.2)	127(81.4)	310(78.9)	.552
	No	53(22.4)	28(17.9)	81(21.6)	
Do you use 2 or more painkillers in combination	Yes	27(11.3)	22(14.1)	49(12.4)	.417
	No	211(88.7)	134(85.9)	345(87.6)	
Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers	Yes	166(42.2)	76(48.7)	166(42.2)	.035
	No	147(62)	80(51.3)	227(57.8)	
Do you use painkillers for causes other than pain	Yes	27(11.3)	13(8.3)	40(10.1)	.340
	No	212(88.7)	143(91.7)	355(89.9)	
Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers	Yes	47(20.1)	33(21.2)	79(21.5)	.664*
	No	191(79.9)	123(78.8)	314(79.5)	
What is the frequency of pain	Daily	35(14.1)	36(23.1)	71(17.5)	.005
	Once in a week	84(33.7)	58(37.2)	142(35.1)	
	Once in a month	125(50.2)	53(34)	178(44)	
	Never	5(2)	9(5.3)	14(3.4)	
Which pain you feel mostly	Headache	99(39.8)	76(48.7)	175(43.2)	.091
	Back pain	64(25.7)	30(19.2)	94(23.2)	
	Leg pain	54(21.7)	24(15.4)	78(19.3)	
	Others	32(12.9)	26(16.7)	58(14.3)	
How do you treat your pain	Rest	52(20.9)	60(38.5)	112(27.7)	.000
	Massage	20(8.0)	7(4.5)	27(6.7)	
	Stroking	9(3.6)	8(5.1)	17(4.2)	
	Medicines	164(65.9)	73(46.8)	237(58.5)	
	Others	4(1.6)	8(5.1)	12(3)	

Table 4.4 continued.....

Statement		Male	Female	Total	P
Which painkiller you use mostly	Panadol	109(45.8)	89(57.1)	198(50.3)	.385
	Ponstan	50(21)	24(15.4)	74(18.8)	
	Dicloran	19(8.0)	12(7.7)	31(7.9)	
	Dispirine	25(10.5)	11(7.1)	36(9.1)	
	Brufen	15(6.3)	10(6.4)	25(6.3)	
	Tramal	9(3.8)	3(1.9)	12(3)	
	Voltral	6(2.5)	2(1.3)	8(2)	
	Others	5(2.1)	5(3.2)	10(2.5)	
Severity of pain that forces you to take painkillers	Severe	147(61.8)	101(64.7)	248(62.9)	.881*
	Moderate	80(33.6)	41(26.3)	121(30.7)	
	Mild	11(4.6)	14(9.0)	25(6.4)	
Reason for choosing a specific painkiller	Prescribed	100(42.0)	52(33.3)	152(38.6)	.239
	Due to availability	44(18.5)	40(25.6)	84(21.3)	
	Previous positive experience	89(37.4)	60(38.5)	149(37.8)	
	Others	5(2.1)	4(2.6)	9(2.3)	
You use painkillers on the advice of	Doctor	124(52.1)	76(48.7)	200(50.8)	.645
	Pharmacists	14(5.9)	7(4.5)	21(5.3)	
	Family/Friends	43(18.1)	36(23.1)	79(20.1)	
	Media	8(3.4)	3(1.9)	11(2.8)	
	Yourself	49(20.6)	34(21.8)	83(21.1)	
What is your preferable dosage form	Tablet/Capsules	185(77.7)	108(69.2)	293(74.4)	.100
	Injections	20(8.4)	12(7.7)	32(8.1)	
	Syrups	29(12.2)	29(18.6)	58(14.7)	
	Others	4(1.7)	7(4.5)	11(2.8)	

Table 4.4 continued.....

Statement		Male	Female	Total	P
You use painkillers with	Water	182(76.8)	135(86.5)	317(80.7)	.109*
	Milk	30(12.7)	8(5.1)	38(9.7)	
	Tea	22(9.3)	10(6.4)	32(8.1)	
	Others	3(1.3)	3(1.9)	6(1.5)	
From where you get your painkillers	Pharmacy	38(15.9)	26(16.7)	64(16.2)	.567
	Medical Stores	149(62.3)	104(66.7)	253(64.1)	
	Govt. Hospitals	24(10)	14(9.0)	38(9.6)	
	Generals Stores	23(9.6)	8(5.1)	31(7.8)	
	Herbal Stores	5(2.1)	4(2.6)	9(2.3)	

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded. Values with * are Fischer exact test values.

1.8 ASSOCIATION OF KNOWLEDGE WITH AGE

Association of age with the knowledge about use of painkillers shows insignificant difference. In section of knowledge towards use of painkillers twelve questions are present. We check the association of age with all these questions. All questions showed insignificant difference. The age group of 18-30(80.7) has the highest knowledge about the fact that painkillers can relieve fatigue. Whereas age group of 61-80 had the lowest knowledge as only 17 respondents answer the question correctly. Similarly in all other questions the age group 18-30 showed the highest knowledge regarding use of painkillers.

1.9 ASSOCIATION OF ATTITUDE WITH AGE

Table 4.5 shows the association of attitude with age there was significant effect of age on attitude. Age group of 18-30 years mostly read about the product information before its use(55.1%). All age groups mostly used their painkillers with water except age group 60-80 years; they have pretty low percentage as compared to others. Most of the people bought their painkillers from medical stores; percentage was low in case of purchases pharmacy. May be this difference was because of the reason that most people weren't aware of the concept of pharmacy. Younger age groups mostly suffered from headache and use of paracetamol was also comparatively high in this group.

Table4.5 ASSOCIATION OF ATTITUDE WITH AGE

Statement		18-30	31-42	43-60	61-80	Total	P.
Do you know the correct dose of painkiller	Yes	102(45.7)	43(46.7)	26(34.7)	7(36.8)	178(43.5)	.312
	No	121(54.3)	49(53.3)	49(65.3)	12(63.2)	231(56.5)	
	Total	223	92	75	19	409	
Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms	Yes	88(39.5)	138(40.9)	37(49.3)	5(26.3)	168(41.0)	.254
	No	135(60.5)	55(59.1)	38(50.7)	14(73.7)	242(59.0)	
	Total	223	93	75	19	410	
Have You ever suffered from pain	Yes	207(92.8)	90(96.8)	75(97.4)	17(89.5)	389(94.4)	.237
	No	16(7.2)	3(3.2)	2(2.6)	2(10.5)	23(5.6)	
	Total	223	93	77	19	412	
Does pain affect your working ability	Yes	174(80.6)	68(78.2)	57(80.3)	12(68.4)	312(79.4)	.081
	No	42(19.4)	19(21.8)	14(19.7)	6(31.6)	81(20.6)	
	Total	216	87	71	19	393	
Do you use 2 or more painkillers in combination	Yes	29(13.5)	12(13.6)	5(6.9)	3(15.8)	49(12.4)	.471
	No	186(86.5)	76(86.4)	67(93.1)	16(84.2)	345(87.6)	
	Total	215	88	72	19	394	
Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers	Yes	118(55.1)	29(33)	16(22.2)	3(15.8)	166(42.2)	.000
	No	96(44.9)	59(67)	56(77.8)	16(84.2)	227(57.8)	
	Total	214	88	72	19	393	
Do you use painkillers for causes other than pain	Yes	19(8.8)	11(12.5)	9(12.5)	1(5.3)	40(10.1)	.593
	No	197(91.2)	77(87.5)	63(87.5)	18(94.7)	355(89.9)	
	Total	216	88	72	19	395	
Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers	Yes	49(22.7)	14(15.9)	12(16.7)	6(31.6)	81(20.5)	.478 *
	No	167(77.3)	74(84.1)	60(83.3)	13(68.4)	314(79.5)	
	Total	216	88	72	19	395	

Table 4.5 continued.....

Statement		18-30	31-42	43-60	61-80	Total	P.
What is the frequency of pain	Daily	33(15.1)	12(13)	19(25.3)	7(36.8)	71(17.5)	.020 *
	Once in a week	67(30.6)	38(41.3)	29(38.7)	8(42.1)	142(35.1)	
	Once in a month	107(48.9)	41(44.6)	27(36)	3(15.8)	178(44)	
	Never	12(5.4)	1(1.1)	0	1(5.3)	14(3.4)	
	Total						
Which pain you feel mostly	Headache	109(49.8)	38(41.3)	23(30.7)	5(26.3)	175(43.2)	.000
	Back pain	42(19.2)	22(23.9)	22(29.3)	8(42.1)	94(23.2)	
	Leg pain	28(12.8)	26(28.3)	21(28)	3(15.8)	78(19.3)	
	Others	40(18.3)	6(6.5)	9(12)	3(15.8)	58(14.3)	
	Total						
How do you treat your pain	Rest	85(38.8)	10(10.9)	16(21.3)	1(5.3)	112(27.7)	.000 *
	Massage	10(4.6)	6(6.5)	9(12.0)	2(10.5)	27(6.7)	
	Stroking	6(2.7)	7(7.6)	2(2.7)	2(10.5)	17(4.2)	
	Medicines	110(50.2)	69(75)	46(61.3)	12(63.2)	237(58.5)	
	Others	8(3.7)	0	2(2.7)	2(10.5)	12(3)	
	Total						
Which painkiller you use mostly	Panadol	124(57.4)	31(35.6)	38(52.8)	5(26.3)	198(50.3)	.001 *
	Ponstan	33(15.3)	20(23.0)	16(22.2)	5(26.3)	74(18.8)	
	Dicloran	15(6.9)	6(6.9)	7(9.7)	3(15.8)	31(7.9)	
	Dispirine	18(8.3)	13(14.9)	5(6.9)	0	36(9.1)	
	Brufen	14(6.5)	9(10.3)	1(1.4)	1(5.3)	25(6.3)	
	Tramal	2(0.9)	5(5.7)	3(4.2)	2(10.5)	12(3.0)	
	Voltral	5(2.3)	2(2.3)	1(1.4)	0	8(2.0)	
	Others	5(2.3)	1(1.1)	1(1.4)	3(15.8)	10(2.5)	
	Total	216(100)	87(100)	72(100)	19(100)	394(100)	
Severity of pain that forces you to take painkillers	Severe	135(62.8)	53(60.2)	50(69.4)	10(52.6)	248(62.90)	.005 *
	Moderate	64(29.8)	31(35.2)	19(26.4)	7(36.8)	121(30.7)	
	Mild	16(7.4)	4(4.5)	3(4.2)	2(10.6)	25(6.4)	
	Total	215(100)	88(100)	72(100)	19(100)	394(100)	
Reason for choosing a specific painkiller	Prescribed	85(39.5)	31(35.2)	27(37.5)	9(47.4)	152(38.6)	.443 *
	Due to availability	38(17.7)	24(27.3)	19(26.4)	3(15.8)	84(21.3)	
	Previous positive experience	85(39.5)	32(36.4)	26(36.1)	6(31.6)	149(37.8)	
	Others	7(3.3)	1(1.1)	0	1(5.3)	9(2.3)	
	Total	215(100)	88(100)	72(100)	19(100)	394(100)	

Table 4.5 continued.....

Statement		18-30	31-42	43-60	61-80	Total	P.
You use painkillers on the advice of	Doctor	124(57.4)	39(44.8)	28(38.9)	9(47.4)	200(50.8)	.047 *
	Pharmacists	9(4.2)	7(8.0)	4(5.6)	1(5.3)	21(5.3)	
	Family/Friends	36(16.7)	19(21.8)	18(25)	6(31.6)	79(20.1)	
	Media	6(2.8)	2(2.3)	3(4.2)	0	11(2.8)	
	Yourself	41(19)	20(23.0)	19(26.4)	3(15.8)	83(21.1)	
	Total	216(100)	87(100)	72(100)	19(100)	394(100)	
What is your preferable dosage form	Tablet/Capsules	160(74.4)	68(77.3)	53(73.6)	12(63.2)	293(74.4)	.961 *
	Injections	12(5.6)	88(9.1)	10(13.9)	2(10.5)	32(8.1)	
	Syrups	35(16.3)	12(13.6)	8(11.1)	3(15.8)	58(14.7)	
	Others	8(3.7)	0	1(1.4)	2(10.5)	11(2.8)	
	Total	215(100)	88	72	19	394	
You use painkillers with	Water	181(84.6)	72(81.8)	53(73.6)	11(57.9)	317(80.7)	.004 *
	Milk	18(8.4)	7(8.0)	8(11.1)	5(26.3)	38(9.7)	
	Tea	12(5.6)	8(9.1)	10(13.9)	2(10.5)	32(8.1)	
	Others	3(1.4)	1(1.1)	1(1.4)	1(5.3)	6(1.5)	
	Total	214	88	72	19	393	
From where you get your painkillers	Pharmacy	40(18.5)	14(15.9)	9(12.5)	1(5.3)	64(16.2)	.001 *
	Medical Stores	148(68.5)	52(59.1)	41(56.9)	12(63.2)	253(64.1)	
	Govt. Hospitals	16(7.4)	9(10.2)	10(13.9)	3(15.8)	38(9.6)	
	Generals Stores	6(2.8)	11(12.5)	12(16.7)	2(10.5)	31(7.8)	
	Herbal Stores	6(2.8)	2(2.3)	0	1(5.3)	9(2.3)	
	Total	216	88	72	19	395	

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded. Values with * are of Fischer exact test.

1.10 ASSOCIATION OF KNOWLEDGE WITH JOB

Association of job with knowledge towards use of painkillers in which all questions showed insignificant difference except the question "can painkiller cause sleep disturbances". The response of employed (yes: 50.6%) was greater than that of unemployed (yes: 67.3 %) which was 0.001.

1.11 ASSOCIATION OF ATTITUDE WITH JOB

Table 4.6 shows association of job with attitude towards use of painkillers. All questions showed insignificant response except the question how you treat your pain with the use of medicine. The response of employed was greater than that of unemployed and the response was near to significant which was 0.002.

Table 4.6 ASSOCIATION OF ATTITUDE WITH JOB

Statement		Employed	Unemployed	Total	P
Do you know the correct dose of painkiller	Yes	93(38.6)	85(56.6)	178(43.5)	.016
	No	148(61.4)	83(49.4)	231(56.1)	
Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms	Yes	108(43.8)	62(36.9)	168(41.0)	.163
	No	136(56.2)	106(63.1)	242(59.0)	
Have You ever suffered from pain	Yes	232(95.1)	157(93.5)	389(94.4)	.479
	No	12(4.9)	11(6.5)	23(5.6)	
Does pain affect your working ability	Yes	175(76.4)	135(82.3)	310(78.9)	.149*
	No	53(23.1)	28(17.1)	81(20.6)	
Do you use 2 or more painkillers in combination	Yes	25(10.9)	24(14.6)	49(12.4)	.264
	No	205(89.1)	140(85.4)	345(87.6)	
Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers	Yes	76(33)	90(55.2)	166(42.2)	≤.001
	No	154(67)	73(44.8)	227(57.8)	
Do you use painkillers for causes	Yes	21(9.1)	19(11.6)	40(10.1)	.418

other than pain	No	210(90.9)	145(88.4)	355(89.9)	
Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers	Yes	41(17.7)	40(24.4)	81(20.5)	.656*
	No	190(82.3)	124(75.6)	314(79.5)	
What is the frequency of pain	Daily	40(16.8)	31(18.6)	71(17.5)	.031
	Once in a week	81(34)	61(36.5)	142(35.1)	
	Once in a month	114(47.9)	64(38.3)	178(44)	
	Never	3(1.3)	11(6.6)	14(3.4)	
Which pain you feel mostly	Headache	97(40.8)	78(46.7)	175(43.2)	.007
	Back pain	62(26.1)	32(19.2)	94(23.2)	
	Leg pain	54(22.7)	24(14.4)	78(19.3)	
	Others	25(10.5)	33(19.8)	58(14.3)	

Table 4.6 Continued.....

Statement		Employed	Unemployed	Total	P
How do you treat your pain	Rest	53(22.3)	59(35.3)	112(27.7)	.002
	Massage	16(6.7)	11(6.6)	27(6.7)	
	Stroking	9(3.8)	8(4.8)	17(4.2)	
	Medicines	157(66)	80(47.9)	237(58.5)	
	Others	3(1.3)	9(5.4)	12(3)	
Which painkiller you use mostly	Panadol	108(47)	90(54.9)	198(50.3)	.157*
	Ponstan	44(19.1)	30(18.3)	74(18.8)	
	Dicloran	21(9.1)	10(6.1)	31(7.9)	
	Dispirine	23(10)	13(7.9)	36(9.1)	
	Brufen	13(5.7)	12(7.3)	25(6.3)	
	Tramal	10(4.3)	2(1.2)	12(3.0)	
	Voltral	4(1.7)	4(2.4)	8(2.0)	
	Others	7(3.0)	3(1.8)	10(2.5)	
Severity of pain that forces you to take painkillers	Severe	145(63)	103(62.8)	248(62.9)	.691*
	Moderate	73(31.7)	48(29.3)	121(30.7)	
	Mild	12(5.3)	13(7.9)	24(6.1)	
Reason for choosing a specific painkiller	Prescribed	97(42.2)	55(33.5)	152(38.6)	.326
	Due to availability	47(20.4)	37(22.6)	84(21.3)	
	Previous positive experience	82(35.7)	67(40.9)	149(37.8)	
	Others	4(1.7)	5(3.0)	9(2.3)	
You use painkillers on the advice of	Doctor	123(53.5)	77(47)	200(50.8)	.106
	Pharmacists	15(6.5)	6(3.7)	21(5.1)	
	Family/Friends	37(16.1)	42(25.6)	79(20.1)	
	Media	8(3.5)	3(1.8)	11(2.8)	
	Yourself	47(20.4)	36(22)	83(21.1)	
What is your preferable dosage form	Tablet/Capsules	182(79.1)	111(67.7)	293(74.4)	.008
	Injections	20(8.7)	12(7.3)	32(8.1)	
	Syrups	24(10.9)	33(20.1)	58(14.7)	
	Others	3(1.3)	8(4.9)	11(2.8)	
You use painkillers with	Water	185(88.8)	132(80.5)	317(80.7)	.756*
	Milk	20(8.7)	18(11)	38(9.7)	
	Tea	20(8.7)	12(7.3)	32(8.1)	
	Others	4(1.7)	2(1.2)	6(1.5)	

Table 4.6 continued.....

Statement		Employed	Unemployed	Total	P
From where you get your painkillers	Pharmacy	39(16.9)	25(15.2)	64(16.2)	.170
	Medical Stores	139(60.2)	114(69.5)	253(64.1)	
	Govt. Hospitals	24(10.4)	14(8.5)	38(9.6)	
	Generals Stores	24(10.4)	7(4.3)	31(7.8)	
	Herbal Stores	5(2.2)	4(2.4)	9(2.3)	

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded. Values with * are of Fischer exact test.

1.12 ASSOCIATION OF INCOME WITH KNOWLEDGE

Association of income with knowledge shows insignificant difference. There wasn't any great influence of income on knowledge, except in question "Is it safe to take painkillers for long term" (No; more than 35000: 87.9%) mostly this category person response was correct. In case of question related to fatigue, respondents with monthly income less than 14000, had highest ratio 87.6% that painkillers can relieve fatigue.

1.13 ASSOCIATION OF INCOME WITH ATTITUDE

Table 4.7 shows the association of income with attitude. There was significant difference in different income groups for some questions. The attitude of respondents was different according to their income the mostly people bought their painkillers from medical store. The ratio of getting painkillers from pharmacy in high the group having monthly income greater than 35000 shows that with the increasing monthly income the attitude changed toward the use of painkillers.

Table 4.7 ASSOCIATION OF INCOME WITH KNOWLEDGE

Statement		<14k N(%)	14k-25k N(%)	26k-35k N(%)	>35K N(%)	Total N(%)	P.
Do you know the correct dose of painkiller	Yes	27(31)	38(47.5)	14(40)	40(44.4)	119(40.8)	.143
	No	60(69)	42(52.5)	21(60)	50(55.6)	173(59.2)	
	Total	87	80	35	90	292	
Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms	Yes	46(52.3)	31(38.8)	17(48.6)	36(40)	130(44.4)	.241
	No	42(47.7)	49(61.3)	18(51.4)	54(60)	163(55.6)	
	Total	88	80	35	90	293	
Have You ever suffered from pain	Yes	83(93.3)	76(95)	34(97.1)	87(95.6)	280(94.9)	.443*
	No	6(6.7)	4(5)	1(2.9)	4(4.4)	15(5.1)	
	Total	89	80	35	91	295	
Does pain affect your working ability	Yes	62(76.5)	58(76.3)	24(68.6)	72(81.8)	64(22.9)	.269 *
	No	19(23.5)	18(23.7)	11(31.4)	16(18.2)	216(77.1)	
	Total	81	76	35	88	280	
Do you use 2 or more painkillers in combination	Yes	9(11)	7(9.3)	6(17.1)	6(6.7)	28(10)	.367
	No	73(89)	68(90.7)	29(82.9)	83(93.3)	253(90)	
	Total	82	75	35	89	281	
Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers	Yes	21(25.6)	28(37.3)	13(37.1)	31(34.8)	93(33.1)	.382
	No	61(74.4)	47(62.7)	22(62.9)	58(65.2)	188(66.9)	
	Total	82	75	35	89	281	
Do you use painkillers for causes other than pain	Yes	4(4.9)	6(7.9)	5(14.3)	6(6.7)	21(7.4)	.355
	No	78(95.1)	70(92.1)	30(85.7)	83(93.3)	261(92.6)	
	Total	82	76	35	89	282	
Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers	Yes	15(18.3.1)	18(23.7)	5(14.3)	12(13.5)	50(17.7)	.384 *
	No	67(81.7)	58(76.3)	30(85.7)	77(86.5)	232(82.3)	
	Total	82	76	35	89	282	
What is the frequency of pain	Daily	18(20.9)	15(19)	9(25.7)	13(14.6)	55(19)	.347 *
	Once in a	27(31.4)	29(36.7)	12(34.3)	25(28.1)	93(32.2)	

	week						
	Once in a month	40(46.5)	35(44.3)	14(40)	46(51.7)	135(46.7)	
	Never	1(1.2)	0	0	5(5.6)	6(2.1)	
	Total	86	79	35	89	289	

Table4.7 continued....

Statement		<14k N(%)	14k-25k N(%)	26k-35k N(%)	>35K N(%)	Total N(%)	P.
Which pain you feel mostly	Headache	37(43)	31(39.2)	12(34.3)	45(50.6)	125(23.3)	.063
	Back pain	23(26.7)	18(22.8)	13(37.1)	16(18)	70(24.2)	
	Leg pain	16(18.6)	22(27.8)	8(22.9)	11(12.4)	57(19.7)	
	Others	10(11.6)	8(10.1)	2(5.7)	17(19.1)	37(12.8)	
	Total	86	79	35	89	289	
How do you treat your pain	Rest	22(25.6)	19(24.1)	6(17.1)	29(32.6)	76(26.3)	.297 *
	Massage	4(4.7)	4(5.1)	5(14.3)	7(7.9)	20(6.9)	
	Stroking	1(1.3)	6(7.6)	1(2.9)	2(2.2)	10(3.5)	
	Medicines	58(67.4)	48(60.8)	23(65.7)	49(55.1)	78(6.1)	
	Others	1(1.2)	2(2.5)	0	2(2.2)	51.7(0)	
Total	86	79	35	89	289		
Which painkiller you use mostly	Panadol	41(50)	28(37.3)	14(40)	58(65.2)	141(50.2)	.089 *
	Ponstan	17(20.7)	19(25.3)	9(25.7)	9(10.1)	54(19.2)	
	Dicloran	6(7.3)	6(8.0)	4(11.4)	7(7.9)	23(8.2)	
	Dispirine	9(11)	10(13.3)	1(2.9)	4(4.5)	24(8.5)	
	Brufen	2(2.4)	5(6.7)	3(8.6)	4(4.5)	14(5.0)	
	Tramal	2(2.4)	4(5.3)	3(8.6)	2(2.2)	11(3.9)	
	Voltral	2(2.4)	1(1.3)	1(2.9)	2(2.2)	6(2.1)	
	Others	3(3.7)	2(2.7)	0	3(3.4)	8(2.8)	
Total	82	75	35	89	281		
Severity of pain that forces you to take painkillers	Severe	56(68.3)	39(59.3)	23(65.7)	63(71.6)	181(64.4)	.006 *
	Moderate	26(31.7)	31(40.8)	10(28.6)	18(20.5)	85(30.2)	
	Mild	0	6(7.9)	2(5.7)	7(8)	15(5.4)	
	Total	82	76	35	88	281	
Reason for choosing a specific painkiller	Prescribed	42(51.2)	23(30.7)	11(31.4)	40(44.9)	116(41.3)	.000
	Due to availability	13(15.9)	26(34.7)	11(31.4)	7(7.9)	57(20.3)	
	Previous positive experience	26(31.7)	25(33.3)	12(34.3)	39(43.8)	102(36.3)	
	Others	1(1.2)	1(1.3)	1(2.9)	3(3.4)	6(2.1)	
Total	82	75	35	89	281		

Table 4.7 continued....

Statement		<14k N(%)	14k-25k N(%)	26k-35k N(%)	>35K N(%)	Total N(%)	P.
You use painkillers on the advice of	Doctor	45(54.9)	31(41.3)	13(37.1)	55(61.8)	144(51.2)	.032 *
	Pharmacists	3(3.7)	5(6.7)	5(14.3)	2(2.2)	15(5.3)	
	Family/Friends	13(15.9)	22(29.3)	9(25.7)	10(11.2)	54(19.2)	
	Media	3(3.7)	1(1.3)	1(2.9)	4(4.5)	9(3.2)	
	Yourself	18(22)	16(23.3)	7(20.0)	18(20.2)	59(21)	
Total	82	75	35	89	281		
What is your preferable dosage form	Tablet/Capsules	64(78)	52(68.4)	26(74.3)	80(90.9)	222(79)	.002 *
	Injections	8(9.8)	8(10.5)	3(8.6)	2(2.3)	21(7.5)	
	Syrups	7(8.5)	15(19.7)	6(17.1)	3(3.4)	31(11)	

	Others	3(3.7)	1(1.3)	0	3(3.4)	7(2.5)	
	Total	82	76	35	88	281	
You use painkillers with	Water	66(82.5)	55(72.4)	27(77.1)	78(87.6)	226(80.7)	.014
	Milk	8(10)	12(15.8)	3(8.6)	2(2.2)	25(8.9)	*
	Tea	6(7.5)	9(11.8)	3(8.6)	6(6.7)	24(8.6)	
	Others	0	0	2(5.7)	3(3.4)	5(1.8)	
	Total	80	76	35	89	280	
From where you get your painkillers	Pharmacy	10(12.2)	6(7.9)	7(20)	25(28.1)	48(17)	.004
	Medical Stores	56(68.3)	45(59.2)	20(57.1)	53(59.6)	174(61.7)	*
	Govt. Hospitals	9(11)	11(14.5)	3(8.6)	3(3.4)	26(9.2)	
	Generals Stores	7(8.5)	12(15.8)	4(11.4)	5(5.6)	28(9.9)	
	Herbal Stores	0	2(2.6)	1(2.9)	3(3.4)	6(2.1)	
	Total	82	76	35	89	282	

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded. Values with * are of Fischer exact test.

1.14 ASSOCIATION OF LEVEL OF EDUCATION WITH ATTITUDE

Table 4.8 shows the association of level of education with attitude. Statistically there was a significant difference. It shows that with increase of education level the attitude become well towards the use of painkillers.

Table4.8 ASSOCIATION LEVEL OF EDUCATION OF WITH ATTITUDE

Table 4.8 continued.....

What is the	Daily	15(46.9)	10(19.2)	12(13.2)	14(15.9)	21(14.7)	72(17.7)	.000
Statement		Illiterate N(%)	Primary N(%)	Sec. N(%)	H. Sec N(%)	Higher N(%)	Total N(%)	P.
Do you know the correct dose of painkiller	Yes	8(23.5)	24(45.3)	38(41.8)	40(45.5)	68(47.6)	178(43.5)	.147
	No	26(76.5)	29(54.7)	53(58.2)	48(54.5)	75(52.4)	231(56.5)	
	Total	34	53	91	88	143	409	
Do you use painkillers in flu symptoms	Yes	15(44.1)	27(50.9)	34(37.0)	35(39.8)	57(39.9)	168(41.0)	.548
	No	19(55.9)	26(49.1)	58(63.0)	53(60.2)	86(60.1)	242(59.0)	
	Total	34	53	92	88	143	410	
Have You ever suffered from pain	Yes	30(88.2)	52(96.3)	88(95.7)	82(93.2)	137(95.1)	389(94.4)	.488
	No	4(11.8)	2(3.7)	4(4.3)	6(6.8)	7(4.9)	23(5.6)	
	Total	34	54	92	88	144	412	
Does pain affect your working ability	Yes	223(74.2)	40(83.3)	64(72.7)	67(78.8)	118(83.7)	312(79.4)	.132
	No	8(25.8)	8(16.7)	24(27.3)	18(21.2)	23(16.3)	81(20.6)	
	Total	31	48	88	85	141	393	
Do you use 2 or more painkillers in combination	Yes	4(13.3)	43(87.8)	12(13.8)	9(10.3)	18(12.8)	49(12.4)	.970
	No	26(86.7)	6(12.2)	75(86.2)	78(89.7)	123(87.2)	345(87.6)	
	Total	30	49	87	87	141	394	
Do you read the product information before the use of painkillers	Yes	3(10)	12(24.5)	33(38.8)	46(52.3)	72(51.1)	166(42.2)	.000
	No	27(90)	37(75.5)	52(61.2)	42(47.7)	69(48.9)	227(57.8)	
	Total	30	49	85	88	141	393	
Do you use painkillers for causes other than pain	Yes	4(13.3)	4(8.2)	6(6.9)	15(17)	11(7.8)	40(10.1)	.135
	No	26(86.7)	45(91.8)	81(93.1)	73(83)	130(92.2)	355(89.9)	
	Total	30	49	87	88	141	395	
Have you ever felt any adverse effects of painkillers	Yes	7(23.3)	7(14.3)	14(16.1)	22(25)	31(22)	81(20.5)	.314
	No	23(76.7)	42(85.7)	73(83.9)	66(75)	110(78)	314(79.5)	
	Total	30	49	87	88	141	395	

frequency of pain	Once in a week	10(31.2)	28(53.8)	35(38.5)	24(27.3)	45(31.7)	142(35.1)	*
	Once in a month	6(18.8)	14(26.9)	42(46.2)	47(53.4)	69(48.6)	178(44.0)	
	Never	1(3.1)	0	2(2.2)	3(3.4)	7(4.9)	13(3.2)	
	Total	32	52	91	88	143	405	
Which pain you feel mostly	Headache	12(37.5)	19(36.5)	34(37.4)	43(48.9)	67(47.2)	175(43.2)	.022
	Back pain	10(31.2)	18(34.6)	22(24.2)	20(22.7)	24(16.9)	94(23.2)	
	Leg pain	8(25)	11(21.2)	24(26.4)	15(17)	20(14.1)	78(19.3)	
	Others	2(6.2)	4(7.7)	11(12.1)	10(11.4)	31(21.8)	58(14.3)	
	Total	32	52	91	88	142	407	

Table 4.8 continued....

How do you	Rest	7(21.9)	9(17.3)	18(19.8)	28(31.8)	50(35.2)	112(27.5)	.132
Statement	Illiterate N(%)	Primary N(%)	Sec. N(%)	H. Sec N(%)	Higher N(%)	Total N(%)	P.	
	Massage	4(12.5)	4(7.7)	5(5.5)	6(6.8)	8(5.6)	27(67)	
	Stroking	1(3.1)	5(9.6)	4(4.4)	4(4.5)	3(2.1)	17(4.2)	
	Medicines	18(56.2)	33(63.5)	63(69.2)	47(53.4)	76(53.5)	237(58.5)	
	Others	2(6.1)	1(1.9)	1(1.1)	3(3.4)	5(31.5)	12(3.0)	
	Total	32	52	91	88	142	405	
Which painkiller you use mostly	Panadol	13(43.3)	21(42.9)	42(48.3)	46(52.9)	76(53.9)	198(50.3)	.366 *
	Ponstan	7(23.3)	9(18.4)	19(21.8)	15(17.2)	24(17)	74(18.8)	
	Dicloran	2(6.7)	7(14.3)	5(5.7)	5(5.7)	12(8.5)	31(7.9)	
	Dispirine	5(16.7)	6(12.2)	7(8)	9(10.3)	9(6.4)	36(9.1)	
	Brufen	1(3.3)	1(2)	6(6.9)	5(5.7)	12(8.5)	25(6.3)	
	Tramal	0	3(6.1)	4(4.6)	4(4.6)	1(0.7)	12(3.0)	
	Voltral	0	0	3(3.4)	3(3.4)	2(1.4)	8(2.0)	
	Others	2(6.7)	2(4.1)	1(1.1)	0	5(3.5)	10(2.5)	
Total	30	49	87	87	141	394		
Severity of pain that forces you to take painkillers	Severe	20(66.7)	32(65.3)	45(51.7)	57(64.8)	94(67.1)	248(62.9)	.113 *
	Moderate	9(30)	17(34.7)	36(41.4)	23(26.1)	36(25.7)	121(30.7)	
	Mild	1(3.3)	0	6(6.8)	8(9.1)	10(7.1)	25(6.4)	
	Total	30	49	87	88	140	394	

Table 4.8 continued.....

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded. Values

You use painkillers on the advice of	Doctor	9(31)	19(38.8)	47(54)	49(55.7)	76(53.9)	200(50.8)	.005 *
	Pharmacists	0	3(6.1)	7(8)	8(9.1)	3(2.1)	21(5.3)	
	Family/Friends	11(37.9)	12(24.5)	20(23)	15(17)	21(14.9)	79(20.1)	
	Media	1(3.4)	3(6.1)	1(1.1)	0	6(4.3)	11(2.8)	
	Yourself	8(27.6)	12(24.5)	12(13.8)	16(18.2)	35(24.8)	83(21.1)	
	Total	29	49	87	88	141	394	
What is your preferable dosage form	Tablet/Capsules	19(63.3)	31(63.3)	68(79.9)	71(80.7)	104(73.8)	293(74.4)	.034 *
	Injections	6(20)	6(12.2)	10.5	5(5.7)	6(4.3)	32(8.1)	
	Syrups	3(10)	11(22.4)	8(9.3)	10(11.4)	26(18.4)	58(14.7)	
	Others	2(6.7)	1(2)	1(1.2)	2(2.3)	5(3.3)	11(2.8)	
	Total	30	49	86	88	141	394	
You use painkillers with	Water	22(73.3)	38(77.6)	66(76.7)	73(83.9)	118(83.7)	317(80.7)	.193 *
	Milk	4(13.3)	7(14.3)	8(9.3)	10(11.5)	9(6.4)	38(9.7)	
	Tea	3(10)	4(8.2)	12(14)	3(3.4)	10(7.1)	32(8.1)	
	Others	1(3.3)	0	0	1(1.1)	4(2.8)	6(1.5)	
	Total	30	49	86	87	141	393	
From where you get your painkillers	Pharmacy	0	2(4.1)	9(10.3)	21(23.9)	32(22.7)	64(16.2)	.000 *
	Medical Stores	21(70)	27(55.1)	58(66.7)	55(62.5)	92(65.2)	253(64.1)	
	Govt. Hospitals	5(16.7)	9(18.4)	9(10.3)	6(6.8)	9(6.4)	38(9.6)	
	Generals Stores	3(10)	9(18.4)	10(11.5)	4(4.5)	5(3.5)	31(7.8)	
	Herbal Stores	1(3.3)	2(4.1)	1(1.1)	2(2.3)	3(2.1)	9(2.3)	
	Total	30	49	87	88	141	395	

with * are of Fischer exact test.

Reason for choosing a specific painkiller	Prescribed	7(23.3)	20(40.8)	40(46.5)	40(45.5)	45(31.9)	152(38.6)	.003 *
	Due to availability	11(36.7)	16(32.7)	18(20.9)	18(20.5)	21(14.9)	84(21.3)	
	Previous positive experience	11(36.7)	12(24.5)	28(32.6)	28(31.8)	70(49.6)	149(37.8)	
	Others	1(3.3)	1(2)	0	2(2.3)	5(3.5)	9(2.3)	
	Total	30	49	86	88	141	394	

1.15 ASSOCIATION OF LEVEL OF EDUCATION WITH KNOWLEDGE

Association of level of education with knowledge shows insignificant difference. It was observed that level of education didn't really influenced knowledge about use of painkillers. Statistically applied p value shows no significant difference in knowledge.

1.16 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST GENDER

The above table 4.9 shows knowledge scoring against gender. It was found that male had more knowledge than the female with the mean rank of 213.41 but the result does not show a great significant difference between the two groups.

Table4.9 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST GENDER

STATEMENT	GENDER	N	MEAN RANK	MANN WHITNEY U	p-value
Knowledge scoring	Male	157	213.41	18932.500	>0.001
	Female	255	202.25		
	Total	412			

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded

1.17 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST AGE

The table 4.10 of knowledge scoring against age shows respondents had no much difference in their knowledge depending on their age. P-value shows insignificant results and age group 61 to 80 had highest mean rank of 215.82.

Table4.10 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST AGE

STATEMENT	AGE	N	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS VALUE	p-vale
Knowledge scoring	18-30	223	209.25	0.830	>0.001
	31-42	93	206.51		
	43-60	77	196.24		
	61-80	19	215.82		
Total	412				

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded

1.18 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST EDUCATION

The above table 14.11 shows the Kruskal Wallis test applied on the education of the respondents. It shows that the respondents with education of higher secondary have the highest mean rank of 138.09 while illiterates had the lowest mean rank of 127.79.

Table4.11 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST EDUCATION

STATEMENT	EDUCATION	N	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS VALUE	p-value
Knowledge scoring	Illiterate	34	127.79	0.945	>0.001
	Primary	54	128.18		
	secondary	92	137.26		
	Higher secondary	88	138.09		

	total	268			
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Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded

1.19 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST JOB

Mann Whitney U test was applied to analyze the knowledge scoring against job. There is an insignificant difference between the both groups. However, employed had more knowledge about the use of painkillers as compared to the unemployed

Table4.12 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST JOB

STATEMENT	RESIDENCE	N	MEAN RANK	MANN WHITNEY U	p-value
Knowledge scoring	Employed	244	203.70	19814.000	>0.001
	Unemployed	168	210.56		
	Total	412			

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded

1.20 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST INCOME

Table4.13 shows the knowledge scoring of respondents with monthly income of more than 35000 PKR had the highest mean rank of 159.94 while respondents with income 14000 to 25000 had the lowest knowledge about the use of painkillers.

Table4.13 KNOWLEDGE SCORING AGAINST FAMILY INCOME

STATEMENT	FAMILY INCOME	N	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS VALUE	p-value
Knowledge scoring	Less than 14000	89	150.04	4.158	>0.001
	14000-25000	80	134.13		
	26000-35000	35	143.46		
	More than 35000	91	159.94		
	Total	295			

Note: All the frequencies and percentages are based upon observed values and missing values were excluded

DISCUSSION:

Although there is a lot of research works on the use of painkillers globally and to some extent in Pakistan. The present study covers the knowledge and attitude towards use of painkillers in Bahawalpur, Pakistan. Most people have knowledge that painkillers can cause allergies. Similar result was found in study conducted in Albania, according to which about half of participants knew that NSAIDs can cause allergy. The result of both studies shows that, respondents are satisfied knowledge regarding painkillers can cause allergies. The same result due to the literacy rate or the level of education that people participated [22]. In present study, more than half participants knew the correct dose of painkillers. But the study conducted in Islamabad- Pakistan, a large number of respondents were unaware of the safe dose for daily use and hence were at the risk of over dose toxicity. The contrary result shows that the awareness about use of correct dose of painkillers are more among respondents of present study as compared to study conducted in Islamabad, Pakistan. The

difference is due to the area of people of lower Punjab and upper Punjab [23].

According to this study, mostly people have knowledge about the painkillers. Majority of the respondents said that painkillers can relieve fatigue and fever. But the response of respondents regarding anti-inflammatory action is less. In our study, the frequency of pain is once a month. Type of pain feel by mostly people is headache. Mostly people get their painkillers from medical store. Most of respondents used their painkillers on the advice of doctor. Same type of study was conducted in Charles University in Prague, Pharmaceutical Faculty, Department of Social and Clinical Pharmacy. According to this study the minority believes that ibuprofen used for fever (7.9%). But response regarding anti-inflammatory action is almost same. In this study, the frequency of pain was that mostly people (64%) suffered from pain every day. Most people use their painkillers on the advice of doctor. The knowledge about the adverse effect of people was poor. The result is almost similar due to illiteracy rate or may be any other factor [24].

The study which was conducted in Italy, most people showed to be aware of the potential gastric damage of NSAIDS. The result of this study is similar as in present study. The respondents of both studies have efficient knowledge regarding that painkillers can cause stomach ulcer. The same results come may be due to the general population and the same methods of study that was conducted [25].

In this study the mostly people knew that painkillers can cause stomach ulcer while a study that was conducted in Turkey showed that about 85.4% and 11.5% of the patients were aware of the GIT and other systems-related adverse effects respectively. The results are almost same due to the same study procedure and literacy rate [26].

In this study, half of participants used painkillers on advice of doctors and few of them take painkillers by their own decisions. While in study which was conducted in Albania, more than half of respondents using painkillers were taking them on their own and only in about 28% of the cases painkillers were recommended by a doctor or a pharmacist. The different result from present study is may be due to less knowledge regarding use of painkillers among respondents of study of Albania. The literacy rate may be less among participants of study which was conducted in Albania as compared to present study [22].

According to our study, 74.1% of respondent's preferred to take painkillers in form of tablets/capsules and others prefer painkillers in form of syrups and injections. Almost similar results are found in study which was conducted in Lublin, the most common form employed was pills. Far fewer take NSAIDS in form of injections and soluble powders. The same result may be due to the thinking of people [11]. While different result was found in study conducted in Nsukka community, sixty percent respondents preferred injectable over oral analgesics. The reason behind this different result may be participants of study wanted quick recovery from pain, therefore preferred injectable over oral analgesics. The participants of study may be unaware of hazards regarding use of injectable dosage form[2].

Another study result matches with present study regarding the preference to take painkillers in form of tablets and pills. The study was conducted in Lublin; we concluded from the responses, the most common form employed was that of pills. a fewer participants took NSAIDS in the form of suppositories, injections and soluble powders [11].

In present study, almost half of participants knew that painkillers can cause shortness of breath. The study conducted in Australia, fewer NSAIDS users identified that NSAIDS should be used with caution

in patient with asthma. The contrary result of study may be because of the little knowledge of respondents regarding side effect of painkillers, which may cause shortness of breath among users [27].

In present study, more than half of participants treated their pain by medicine and few respondents treat their pain by taking rest, which is 27.7% and 6.7% participants treat their pain by taking massage. The similar study was conducted in Tanzania, same result was found that more than half of respondents (52%) said that when they had pain, they bought painkillers from pharmacies, while 1% performed massage at the site of pain which was found less than our study[26].

In this study most of people used their painkillers on the advice of doctor. Same type of study was conducted in COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Abbottabad 22060, Pakistan. Their result about this type of question was same as our study. But in this study the ratio of respondents who used their painkiller by purchasing from a pharmacy on their own behalf was more(38%) while in our study this percentage was less. Reason for this change is that they conducted their study in university teachers including pharmacy department hence therefore this ratio has been increased due to pharmacist [28].

In our study most of people knew the correct dose of painkillers. Knowledge about the use of pain killers is good. Mostly people don't read the leaflets before the use of product. Mostly people don't feel any adverse effect of pain killers. A study was conducted among the different university students of Poland;the result of this study was different. People was not aware about the correct dose(57.4%), knowledge was low, the student of medical field have more positive response as compared to other students regarding the reading of leaflet before the use of product. The result is different may be due to region and the conditions under which the study was conducted [12].

In our study the mostly people knew that long term use of painkillers can cause liver damage. Mostly used painkiller is Panadol (paracetamol). While a study was conducted in NUMS Islamabad-Pakistan the mostly used painkiller was Mefenamic acid (40.8%) and only 28% were aware of liver damage by paracetamol toxicity. Difference in result is due to region and the respondents in our study, the respondents were general public while in this study the respondents were students of university [29].

In present study, the frequency of pain experienced by most of the participants is once a month, while 17.5% experience pain every day and far few never experience pain. Different result is found in study which was conducted in Czech Republic, 7.5%

experienced pain once a month, sixty four percent of respondents suffered from pain nearly every day and only 7.5% never experienced pain. The different result shows that more respondents of Czech Republic suffer with pain daily as compared to our present study. This result reflects that may be the respondents of present study are healthier as respondents of Czech Republic study. The reason is that because the respondents of mentioned study experienced more frequency of pain as frequency exists in present study[24].

In present study, that is conducted in the general public of Bahawalpur the mostly used painkiller is Panadol (paracetamol). Same result was found when a study was conducted in Delhi, India on self-medication the mostly used painkiller was paracetamol. Same result may be due to the people of same continent [30].

In present study, most of the respondents (43.2) felt headache and few felt back pain. Almost similar results were found in study which was conducted in Tanzania, most of people (54%) suffered from headache.[26]. On the other hand, the study which was conducted in Czech Republic, the common site of pain was back and lower back pain and 14% experienced headache [24].

Another study shows the same result as in present study regarding most respondents felt headache pain. The study was conducted in Deccan College of Medical Sciences, most of participants suffered with headache pain followed by lower backache. The most of respondents of both studies take painkillers for headache [30]. Same result show in another study which was conducted in Karachi, Pakistan. The result showed that Headaches were experienced by 87.8% of respondents. The result of this study has higher percentage of respondent that suffer with headache as compared to present study. The reason is may be due to medical students were included in this study. While in present study, respondents were from general population [6].

In present study, 80.9% participants responded that painkillers are not safe in pregnancy. The study which was conducted in Pakistan, 19% people responded that paracetamol and aspirin were given in pregnancy ,13% did not consider taking any such drugs during pregnancy safe while 68% were unaware of the use[29].

In present study, more than half participants knew the correct dose of painkillers. But the study conducted in Islamabad- Pakistan, a large number of

respondents were unaware of the safe dose for daily use and hence were at the risk of over dose toxicity. The contrary result shows that the awareness about use of correct dose of painkillers are more among respondents of present study as compared to study conducted in Islamabad, Pakistan[29].

In present study, only few persons responded that it is safe to use painkillers for long term. The similar study was conducted in Lublin; some participants stated that they take painkillers for longer periods of time and stated that they have a psychological dependence upon them. The result of present study match with the study conducted in Lublin. The respondents of both studies have satisfied knowledge regarding that it is not safe to use painkillers for long time [11].

In present study, the question asks to the participants do you read the product information before the use of painkillers, the less than half of the participants says, they read the product information before the use of painkillers. The different result was found in study which was conducted in Northern Ireland; the majority of respondents were (86.4%) always or often follow the directions on the product. The awareness about reading the product information before the use of painkillers is less in present study. The different result is may be due to literacy rate, which is higher in Northern Ireland as compared to present study [31]. Contrary result also finds in study which was conducted in Jordan. More than half of the respondents were stated that they would always follow the directions on the packet of the OTC product. While in present study, less than half of the respondents said that they read the product information before the use of painkillers. This is may be due to less awareness of respondents of present study [32].

In present study, most participants bought their painkillers from medical stores, few participants get their painkillers from pharmacy followed by very few respondents get their painkillers from general stores, government hospitals, and herbal stores. Contrary result was found in study which was conducted in Netherlands; most consumers prefer painkillers to be available exclusively in pharmacies. This different result reflects that the participants of Netherlands study have awareness of pharmacies, where pharmacists were available. While in present study, the participants have less awareness regarding the importance of pharmacies. This is may be due to present study location is included in developing countries and setup of pharmacies are still not well established [33].

In our study the use of Brufen as a painkiller was less while a study that was conducted in Nagpur a tertiary care hospital the Brufen was most commonly (62.79%) prescribed drug in NSAIDS class. The difference due to the region and the area of the study conducted [17].

In another study, similar results were found which was conducted in Pakistan, the paracetamol was most frequently used painkiller among the respondents but the frequency was higher in this study as compared to present study[34]. A study which was conducted in North-eastern Romania, the result showed that most frequently used painkiller among participants was paracetamol. The result of this study match with the present study [35].

In present study, the most of respondents give reason for choosing a specific painkiller based on doctor suggestion and previous positive exposure followed by due to availability. Almost same results were found in study which was conducted in Northern Ireland; firstly, the most of participants were influenced by how effective they thought the product was, when they were decided to buy OTC medicines. Secondly, the mostly used methods of determining effectiveness were included previous positive exposure and recommended by doctor [36].

In present study, the most of respondents said that the use of painkillers among less than twelve years children is inappropriate. While the study which was conducted in Norway, influenced that high consumption of analgesics and frequent pain may be the warning sign of adolescents affecting health and reduces quality of life. Therefore, painkillers should give with caution in children less than twelve years old [37].

In present study, more than half of respondents don't use painkillers in flu. But the study conducted in university students of Karachi, 65.5 % respondents used painkillers in flu. The significant difference in result exists between the present study and the study conducted in Karachi, Pakistan. This may be due to the literacy rate present between the respondents of two studies. Because the respondents of study conducted in Karachi are university students while in present study are general population[38].

In present study, the most of respondents say that pain affect their work ability. Hence, pain affects their normal life activity. Similar result was found in study which was conducted in Canada, elder respondent's daily life activities were majorly affected by chronic pain. The difference is that in

study of Canada include elder population but in present study include general population. Therefore, the pain affect the normal life activity in general population is an alarming situation[39].

In present study, the few respondents experience adverse effects. Similar result was found in study which was conducted among English students to determine the reason for the use of mild analgesics. A few respondents were indicated that there were short-term risks of using mild analgesics. In both studies, the few respondents are ever felt adverse effect of painkiller [40]. Another study which was conducted in Poland which showed that Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are responsible for 21–25% of reported adverse drug events which include immunological and no immunological hypersensitivity reactions. The percentage of adverse effect in this study is little bit higher than the present study. The reason is may be due to well established pharmacovigilance reported programme exist in Poland as compared to present study. The respondents of Poland study may be more aware of adverse drug events as compared to present study [41].

Another study which was conducted in India, the result showed that very few respondents of study experienced adverse effect of painkillers. Most of these patients were old aged who regularly takes NSAIDs for joint pain [17].

In our study the knowledge about the painkillers and their adverse effect of younger and educated people was more as compared to illiterate and old age people. Same type of study was conducted on just one painkiller BRUFEN in Abbottabad, Pakistan there result was same as our study. The similarity is due to same procedure which is adopted for study and also due to same country [42].

In our study the very less respondents said that they take their painkillers by the media advertisement and T.V. while a study that was conducted in Department of Public Health, Medical University of Warsaw, Poland most of the respondents (51.71%) claim that TV commercial has an influence on their purchasing decisions of OTC analgesics. The difference is due to the place of study and population of study. The study was online and all respondents was students instead of general public [43].

In this study most of people said that they have suffered from pain and bought their painkillers from medical store while a study was conducted in Ilala Municipality, Dar es Salaam they have just 52%

respondents who were ever suffered from pain and bought their painkillers from pharmacies. The difference in result is due to the difference in attitude of people of community [26].

CONCLUSIONS:

Based on the study findings, it is concluded that majority had knowledge about the use and side effect of painkillers and they had positive attitude towards painkiller but some people had no sufficient knowledge about the certain aspects of painkillers i.e. most of people didn't know about the anti-inflammatory effects of painkillers they simply just replied in no. They could get more benefit from the painkillers if they knew about the anti-inflammatory effects of painkillers. Most of the respondents didn't read any kind of information before using painkillers, there were only small number of people those who read the information; this gives us the idea that people were not careful about the use of painkillers or they were not being guided about the proper use of medicines. Most of the people were well aware of adverse effects of painkillers. People also showed the lack of knowledge about the concept of pharmacy. Only small number of people felt the adverse effects, most of those adverse effects were stomach disturbances and allergies. From this study it is concluded that most of the people had sufficient knowledge but their attitude about the usage of painkillers was not good enough. Therefore there is a need of for the proper guidance to patients about the usage of painkillers.

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